

**ROLE OF EDUCATION IN CULTURAL DIVERSITY WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO
CLASSROOM TEACHING****Dr. Usha Vishnu Bhandare***Assistant Professor, Dept. of Commerce**K.B.College Arts and commerce for women, Thane***Abstract**

India is one nation, but a plural society. Its plurality is in built in its geographical, demographic, and historical and so on. Cultural diversity is significant because our country, workplaces and schools increasingly consist of various cultural, racial and ethnic groups. In cultural diversity, we learn from one another, learning about others culture helps us understand different perspective within the world in which we live and also helps dispel negative stereotypes and personal biases about different groups. Through interacting to each other, we can build bridges to trust, respect and understanding the culture of all over the world. The diverse cultures contribute languages skills, new way of thinking, new knowledge and different experiences. Education also plays a central role in conserving, modifying and transforming identities. Keeping in mind the heterogeneous character of Indian society, the national policy on education envisages harmonious development of all groups. Similarly, business organization also plays an important role in cultural diversity through appointing a different religion, race and skill of employees. Social media is also not exceptional. Social media provide a place where people across the world can stay in touch and feel closer and more connected regardless of the distance that separates them. New social media have been rapidly spreading across the globe and gaining popularity in today's society. While providing a common way of linking people together through knowledge, behaviors, and attitudes, a sense of belonging to a greater social network other than one's own local community is effectively created. Hence, it is essential to find out the role of education, organization and social media in cultural diversity.

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Introduction

'Diversity is the one true thing we have in common. Celebrate it every day'-Winston Churchill

Cultural diversity is the quality of diverse or different cultures, as opposed to monoculture, the global monoculture, or a homogenization of cultures, akin to cultural decay. The phrase cultural diversity can also refer to having different cultures respect each other's differences.¹Cultural diversity increases our level of understanding about other cultures through interacting with people outside of our own cultures. Cultural diversity helps to recognize and understand

¹ <https://www.purdueglobal.edu/blog/social-behavioral-sciences/what-is-cultural-diversity/>

that concepts within the helping profession, such as family, gender roles, spirituality, and emotional well-being, vary significantly among cultures and influence behavior. It also supports the idea that every person can make a unique and positive contribution to the larger society because of rather than in spite of their differences.

Objectives of the study:

1. To understand the concept of cultural diversity
2. To find out the role of education in cultural diversity.
3. To Study the importance of classroom teaching in cultural diversity
4. To suggest some strategies to be used to manage cultural diversity in the classroom

Research Methodology

Data Sources: The research paper is purely based on secondary data collected through research article, research paper published in different journal, encyclopedia, newspaper are the additional sources used.

Concept of Cultural Diversity

Cultural diversity is important because our country, workplaces, and schools increasingly consist of various cultural, racial, and ethnic groups. We can learn from one another, but first we must have a level of understanding about each other in order to facilitate collaboration and cooperation.

Education and Culture:

Education is an instrument of cultural change. Education plays a vital role in introducing the culture of the society among the students. Education is a process by which the society through schools, colleges, universities and other institutions deliberately transmits its cultural heritage. Culture is the content of education and has a bearing on the school administration.

Education is a tool through which teachers can impart knowledge, training and skills as well as inculcate new ideas and attitudes among the young. Culture plays an important role in the life of a person. To understand the nature of its importance, it will be easy to understand how education of various elements of culture can help a person. Culture influences the physical, mental, moral, social, aesthetic and emotional aspects of individual. Thus, the behaviour of the individual is greatly influenced by the culture. Education is obviously reflection of the social, cultural and political conditions prevailing outside. It reflects the society but it has within it the seeds of dynamics of change and thus can keep pace with the fast changing world. The schools thus are not blind followers of the dictates of the society but when it degenerates they can improve it and enthuse it with new idea of thought and new horizons of desirable ideals. The school play important role in inculcating culture among young generation. The school has to give up its ivory tower isolation. It must be closely linked with the society. "The starting point of educational reform must be the relinking of the school to life and restoring the intimate relationship between them which has broken down with the development of the formal tradition of education," recommends the Secondary Education Commission.

Importance of Classroom teaching in Cultural Diversity

The school education is very important for the development and upliftment of any individuals in their life. Students who learn about different cultures during their education feel more comfortable and safe with these differences later in life. This allows them to interact in a wider range of social groups and feel more confident in themselves as well as in their interactions with others. Teaching diversity exposes students to various cultural and social groups,

preparing students to become better citizens in their communities. These culturally responsive teaching strategies will help to promote diversity in the classroom.

➤ **Students Become Sensitized**

By understanding the problems and providing supporting hands during the emergency to each other can enable students to become more sensible towards other feeling. They can understand that it is very essential to understand to one through empathetically rather than sympathetically. Classroom teaching can also prevent students from developing prejudices later in life.

➤ **Students can use their strengths to contribute in diverse working environment**

When working and learning with people from a variety of backgrounds and cultures present in the classroom, students gain a more comprehensive understanding of the subject matter. It also teaches students how to use their own strengths and points of view to contribute in a diverse working environment.

➤ **Students Become More Open-Minded**

Naturally, by exposing students to a diverse range of opinions, thoughts, and cultural backgrounds, teacher's can encouraged them to be more open-minded later in life. This will make them open to new ideas and be able to attain a greater comprehension on a topic by taking in different points of view.

➤ **Students Feel More Confident and Safe**

Students who learn about different cultures during their education feel more comfortable and safe with these differences later in life. This allows them to interact in a wider range of social groups and feel more confident in themselves as well as in their interactions with others.

➤ **Students Are Better Prepared for a Diverse Workplace**

With the rise of globalization, it's more important to be able to work with people from different cultures and social groups. If students are exposed to diversity and learn cultural awareness in the classroom, it sets them up to flourish in the workforce.

Role of social media in cultural diversity:

Now a day's new social media is an important part of our lives as it supports us to connect to each other of our culturally diverse world. Media for social interaction allows for people to communicate and engage with information that is quickly accessible on the Internet. The diffusion of new social media across the world has different effects on individual cultures but ultimately promotes interconnectedness and understanding among global societies. In today's society, there is an increasing number of Internet users so new social media has become more popular in daily patterns and routines. The communication that occurs in these online contexts promotes interactive dialogues that build understanding of different points of view.² There are four popular social media i.e. Facebook, Youtube, twitter and iPhone which are largely used by the people to interact to each other to share information, messages, videos and audio etc.

²<https://digitalcommons.uri.edu/>

Literature Review:

Fernando N(2013)³ : This article discusses a classroom project that requires pre-service teachers to use media literacy as a way to cross cultural borders and help diminish the gap between cultures and groups in classrooms and schools. The project was a pedagogical strategy aimed at creating an opportunity and a reason for students to reach out and to experience different ways of seeing the world and interpreting cultural phenomena. Initial assessment from the project suggests that pre-service teachers increased their awareness of the potential of social networks and online learning platforms in helping students cross cultural borders and participate in different cultural communities.

Ines Gil Jaurena(2010)⁴ : A focus of the paper was to describe and analyze a case that was considered a culture blind perspective from the institutional point of view and its effect in the social encounters prompted in the school, including educational decisions that affected culturally diverse students.

Strategies to manage Diversity in the classroom

- It is essential to create awareness among the students about cultural diversity hence, teacher should understand the cultural background, hobbies, learning style of individual students in the class.
- Teacher should also continue to maintain ongoing communication throughout the semester or school year. By organizing quiz, debate or elocution on the topic of cultural diversity, will definitely provide help to teacher to understand the students point of view towards the concept of cultural diversity.
- Celebration of festivals such as Diwali, X'mas, Eid etc definitely help to students to understand each other's religion as well as traditions which also help to create awareness among the students about cultural diversity.
- It's important to keep an open dialogue amongst students, it's equally as important to make sure you're being sensitive to everyone's culture, beliefs, and language concerns. Take the time to understand each student's cultural nuances – from learning styles to the language they use – and use these insights to design your lesson plans.
- There are several ways you can ingrain cultural awareness and diversity into your lesson plan, and it will vary depending on the cultures represented in your classroom and the course you're teaching. Regardless of the subject, always try to present and connect lessons to real-world issues. It's easier to promote cultural awareness within your lessons when there's a real example for students to relate to.
- Allow students to read and present their own materials that relate to the fundamental lesson so they can approach the topic from their own perspective. As a teacher, as act as a facilitator and encourage conversation and healthy debate between diverse opinions. Group assignments are also a great way to expose students to diverse perspectives, allowing students to work together to explore and solve a problem. This will also help prepare them for a diverse workforce where they'll have to partner with a range of people to accomplish their professional goals.

³Naidtch, F. (2013). A Media Literate Approach to Developing Diversity Education. *The National Association for Media Literacy Education's* , 337-348.

⁴Gil,Ines (2010, september). School and cultural diversity: from culture blind perspectives to responsive education. 183-192.

Limitation of the study

The research paper is based on secondary data. Due to time constrain and current Covid pandemic situation the researcher could not collect the data from students which would definitely to find out the perception of students towards cultural diversity.

Conclusion

Diversity in India is endless and unique. It ranges from geographic to demographic features to customs, religious, tradition and languages. Indian society is immensely diverse but at the same times there are bonds of unity and mechanisms of integration that gives a unique character of this country. The term culture can be annotates in different ways like Punjab culture, American culture and at the same time it can be used as a entertainment like cultural programme. Eventually, it is important and essential that bonds of unity and integration go together for longer period of time. Hence, the people should know the custom, tradition and culture of each other's so that it leads to respect and love and affection to each other. If you want to survive in this world, one should know the importance of each other's custom, tradition and culture. In school and colleges, the role of teacher is very important to create awareness of cultural diversity among the students, because today's youth is the power of tomorrows future.

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